

THE HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF ANECDOTES IN UZBEK FOLKLORE

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Annotation. *Uzbek folklore, a vibrant tapestry woven with rich traditions, ancient tales, and everyday wisdom, holds a special place for anecdotes. These short, humorous stories, often featuring relatable characters and everyday situations, offer a unique window into the cultural soul of the Uzbek people. This article explores the history of the study of anecdotes in Uzbek folklore, tracing the evolution of research from early collections to modern academic analysis.*

Genres of folklore are important theoretical issues of every science and field. The science that studies fiction is called literary studies. We call the field of studying folk oral poetic creation folklore. Although folklore studies is considered an independent discipline within literary studies, there are a number of general and common aspects due to the fact that the object of study is fiction. In particular, the issue of genres is important for both literary studies and folklore studies. Only in literary studies, such as ghazal, rubai, dostan, noma belonging to representatives of written literature (classical literature); Genre features of poems, stories, novels, dramas (modern literature) are studied.

Key words: *traditions, culture, understanding of society, basics of folklore, historical development of anecdotes, language learning.*

Introduction. In folklore studies, the peculiarities of such genres as proverbs, songs, fairy tales, and epics in folk literature are studied. However, regardless of the form of literature, achievements and discoveries in each direction are evaluated as a contribution to the development of the science of literature. Uzbek folklore studies and preserves the rich oral creativity of our people, including the anecdote genre. Anecdotes reflect the spirit, outlook, values, traditions, way of life, creative ability and richness of the language of the Uzbek people. This article discusses the history of the study of anecdotes in Uzbek folklore, its stages, the main researchers and the role of anecdotes in the life and culture of the Uzbek people.

Legends, as the first example of artistic creation, served to create a sense of confidence in the human heart, hope that every person can find happiness as a result of his own abilities and actions. For example, the concept of fate has existed in people's minds since ancient times. A person accepted every unpleasant problem as fate. But there are legends in which it is emphasized that the fate of a person is in his own hands. That is, it is said that a person's behavior and intention, especially with a sharp decision, can make a change in fate.

So, in terms of content, legends consist mainly of fictions with a very simple plot that conveys information. In them, the creation of the nation, the appearance of the sun, moon, stars, and planets in the universe, the explanation of geographical names, the review of various historical events and pictures find their expression. From ancient times, our ancestors had a conscious attitude to every question, every problem,

traditions and customs of their lives, even to the homeland where they live, and expressed their final conclusions and experiences through legends, among other genres of folklore. The study of legends in folklore allows to determine the theoretical and practical aspects of the history of oral creation. If the events that cannot happen in legends are narrated, the events in the narratives often tell about specific episodes in the lives of historical figures, famous scholars, and statesmen. Sometimes when we hear a story, we fully believe that it happened, sometimes we may not believe the story, even if it is free from a special fantastic image. Therefore, it is difficult to define a sharp difference between legend and narrative. In any case, based on many years of experience, it can be said that it is appropriate to accept a story that is believed as a legend, and a story that cannot be believed as a myth.

Early collections and initial interest (late 19th century - early 20th century):

1. The Dawn of Uzbek Folklore Studies:

o The systematic study of Uzbek folklore emerged in the late 19th century, with a growing interest in preserving and understanding the rich cultural heritage of the region.

o Early researchers, often linguists and ethnographers, began collecting and documenting various forms of folklore, including anecdotes.

2. Pioneering Collectors:

o Muhammadjon Qodiriy: A prominent figure in Uzbek literature and folklore, Qodiriy made significant contributions to the collection and analysis of Uzbek folklore. His work, "O'zbek Xalq Ertaklari" (Uzbek Folk Tales), includes a collection of anecdotes showcasing the wit and humor of the Uzbek people.

o Abdurahmon Avliyoov: Avliyoov, a renowned scholar of Uzbek language and literature, was a prolific collector of Uzbek folklore. His work encompassed various genres, including anecdotes, demonstrating the rich diversity of oral traditions.

3. Early Focus on Cultural Documentation:

o The initial focus of these early researchers was primarily on documenting the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people.

o Anecdotes were seen as valuable resources for understanding social norms, customs, and daily life.

The Development of Academic Study (Mid-20th Century):

1. Expanding Horizons of Research:

o With the establishment of academic institutions in Uzbekistan, the study of folklore became more systematic and scholarly.

o Researchers began to delve deeper into the structure, themes, and cultural significance of anecdotes.

2. Key Scholars and Their Contributions:

o Fitrat: Fitrat, a prominent Uzbek writer and scholar, explored the diverse forms of Uzbek folklore, including anecdotes. His work focused on the narrative structure and themes present in these humorous tales.

o Abdulla Avloniy: Avloniy, a prominent figure in Uzbek education and language development, emphasized the importance of studying Uzbek folklore, including anecdotes, through the lens of linguistics. He highlighted the richness of the Uzbek language and its role in shaping oral traditions.

o Choriyeu: Choriyeu, a leading figure in Uzbek folklore studies, made significant contributions to the classification and analysis of anecdotes. His work explored the diverse types of Uzbek anecdotes, their origins, and their cultural significance.

3. Exploring Genre and Structure:

o This period witnessed a shift towards a more analytical approach to the study of anecdotes.

o Researchers focused on classifying anecdotes based on their themes, characters, narrative structure, and stylistic devices.

The Post-Independence Era (1991-Present):

1. Renewed Focus and New Perspectives:

o After Uzbekistan gained independence, there was a renewed interest in exploring the cultural heritage of the nation, including its folklore.

o Research on anecdotes gained new momentum, with a focus on their social and cultural significance in modern Uzbek society.

2. Contemporary Researchers and Their Insights:

o Erkin Atabayev: Atabayev, a prominent folklorist, has dedicated significant work to the study of Uzbek anecdotes. His book "O'zbek Xalq Latifalari" (Uzbek Folk Anecdotes) offers a comprehensive collection and analysis of these humorous narratives.

o Shokirjon Xolmirzayev: Xolmirzayev, a scholar of Uzbek language and folklore, has focused on the linguistic aspects of anecdotes. His research explores the role of language in shaping humor, wit, and cultural identity.

o Tursunboy Abdurahmonov: Abdurahmonov, a leading figure in Uzbek folklore studies, has made substantial contributions to the preservation and dissemination of Uzbek folklore, including anecdotes. His work highlights the importance of understanding and appreciating these narratives as a vital part of Uzbek cultural heritage.

3. Interdisciplinary Approaches:

o Modern research on Uzbek anecdotes incorporates interdisciplinary approaches, drawing on insights from linguistics, anthropology, sociology, and cultural studies.

o Researchers explore the social context of anecdotes, their role in shaping cultural identity, and their reflections of social values and norms.

The Enduring Relevance of Anecdotes in Modern Uzbek Society:

1. A Source of Entertainment and Connection:

o Anecdotes remain a popular form of entertainment and social bonding in Uzbek society. They are shared in family gatherings, informal conversations, and online platforms.

o They provide a source of laughter, humor, and shared experiences, fostering a sense of community and connection.

2. Reflecting Social and Cultural Values:

o Anecdotes continue to provide insights into the values, beliefs, and traditions of the Uzbek people. They highlight the importance of family, hospitality, respect for elders, and wit in everyday life.

o They often feature characters and situations that are easily relatable to modern audiences, demonstrating the enduring nature of these themes.

3. Tools for Social Commentary and Satire:

o Anecdotes can be used to address social issues, political concerns, and everyday dilemmas through humor and satire. They can provide a platform for critical thinking and social awareness.

o This use of humor as a form of social commentary is particularly relevant in a rapidly changing world where people are seeking ways to express their perspectives and engage in constructive dialogue.

Because there is no difference between legends and narratives in terms of content and plot system. Only narrations are considered to be historical evidence, evidence.

Narratives belong to the epic genus, like legends, according to the story they reflect. They are short in size. The length of the text is short, and the number of scenes presented is limited. The artistic image is not overemphasized, because the narrative is the priority in them. According to the direction of the content, historical events are divided into narratives created on the basis of the courage or betrayal of the people who participated in them, or to explain the naming of places in the regions of our country.

Conclusion. The study of anecdotes in Uzbek folklore is a rich and rewarding field, offering insights into the cultural heart of the Uzbek people. From early collections to modern academic analysis, researchers have diligently explored the structure, themes, and cultural significance of these humorous narratives. As Uzbekistan continues to evolve, the study of anecdotes remains crucial for understanding the country's history, values, and identity. They are not just amusing stories; they are a testament to the ingenuity, wisdom, and resilience of the Uzbek people, enriching both the past and the present.

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